
Utilizing Electronic Copy Board Machine to Enhance Early Childhood Care Education Pre-Service Teachers Academic Achievement and Interest in Mathematics

BY

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Abstract

The study investigated the utilizing electronic copy board machine to enhance early childhood care Education Pre- Service Teachers Academic Achievement and Interest in Mathematics. Quasi experimental research design involving pretest-posttest nonequivalent group design was adopted. Based on the objectives, three research questions and two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population comprises all 1,763 Pre-service teachers in school of early childhood care education in Alvan Ikoku Federal university of Education in Owerri Municipal Council of Imo state. A sample of two hundred and twenty-two (212) pre-service teachers participated in the study using simple random sampling technique. The instruments used for data collection were researcher made Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) and Mathematics interest Scale Questionnaire (MISQ) which were validated by two expert judges from mathematics education and one expert from measurement and evaluation departments. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Kuder Richardson (KR-20) for MAT and Cronbach alpha for MISQ which yielded a value of 0.76 and 0.89 respectively. The data generated was analyzed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions while ANCOVA were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results show that electronic copy board enhances pre-service teacher's achievement and positive interest in mathematics irrespective of gender. Based on the findings, it was recommended that workshops and seminars should be organized for mathematics teachers on how to utilize electronic copy board machine.

Keywords: Mathematics, Electronic Copy Board Machine, Interest and Academic Achievement

Introduction

Education is the light that drives away the darkness of ignorance and enables mankind to find its way through the tortures and labyrinth of development and civilization (Ikechukwu in Ezechukwu, Ihekoromadu & Obichini, 2017). It is an organized and sustained instruction designed to communicate a combination of knowledge, skills, understanding and values for all activities of life (Abubakar, 2013). It is the process by which man solves his problems to improve his life and make it comfortable. Education is a formidable tool as well as one of the several ways that man employs to bring change in his all-round development. According to Ughamadu (2006) education is the means by which the individual is developed so that he will be able to live effectively and efficiently in the present society and contribute to its advancement and upliftment. Indeed, it is the systematic process of developing individual physically, mentally, emotionally and socially for his own benefit and for the benefit of the society in which he lives. Education is a force towards socio-economic and political transformation as well as a key to achieving sustainable development. One aspect of education where all these are achievable is mathematics education.

Mathematics is a science of magnitude and number as well as the science that sustains the daily practices of man. It is the only core science subject that acts as pivot on which national development and wealth of any nation is created. Competency in mathematics learning is vital and sustainable to every individual's meaningful and productive life. Mathematics learning is very important in enhancement and sustainability of human existence because mathematics is all about finding solutions to human problems and physical challenges. All these are indications that mathematics is useful in domestic and business deals, scientific discoveries, technological breakthrough, problem-solving and decision making in different situations in life (Usman and Nwoye, 2010; Unodiaku, 2012; and National Council of Teachers of Mathematics, (NCTM, 2013). It may be due to this vital usefulness of mathematics that Nigeria government made the study of mathematics compulsory at all levels of education as contained in the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013). Despite the importance accorded to mathematics, the teaching and learning of mathematics in Nigeria primary school level has continued to witness poor performance and challenges. A multiple of causes for the student's low performance in mathematics has been attributed to: difficulty in understanding the specialized mathematical language (Barton & Heidema, 2002; Oyaya & Njuguna, 1999; Battisa & Clements, 1996; O'connor, Kanja & Baba, 2000), ineffective, teacher-centered teaching methods and learners' negative attitudes towards the subject (Miheho, 2012; Ngeno & Changeiywo, 2007), Learners lack of motivation to learn the subject (Githua & Mwangi, 2003) and lack of mathematics syllabus coverage (Shikuku, 2009). Also, Augustine (2010) observed that the field of mathematics has placed too little value on the importance of information and communication technology. He further opined that the best methods to help students enhance better learning and understanding of mathematics is for the teacher to use appropriate teaching technologies which must be student- centered and one of the technologies being advocated in this study is electronic copy board machine.

The electronic copy board machine is a technology that allows the teacher to write on the sides of the board. Copy board is a simple but powerful tool which maximizes results of the learning process. In the electronic copy board machine, the teacher writes directly on the panel surface of the Copy board take notes, draw diagrams and brainstorm. It has the capacity to retain your work and the option of printing or electronically storing what has been written on the board. The teacher can simply scroll to a clean panel, allowing you to continue writing without losing your current work or your train of thought. Electronic copy board machine can

help reduce paper use in the classroom. Copy machines have the ability to print or copy on both sides of the paper which will help very students to get a copy the topic after the learning process. It helps in engaging and knowledge building of students when they are given the opportunity to interact in a physical and mental way in the learning environment. (Suvorov 2015). Through electronic copy board machine, they can share their ideas, experiences and investigations. This method is effective for all students especially for student with low learning speed and even for those with high learning speed. During the use of electronic copy board machine classroom, efficiency increases since student's attention is 100% on learning rather than on his notes and spellings. It makes the shift to digital instructional materials (Bailey et al, 2013). The activities provide students with an active process that gives significant meaning to them. Effective pedagogical practices and use of technology will naturally motivate the students. Students with self-directed learning practices will create an active learning environment; the use during the learning practices can affect self-motivation to improve the quality of the learning. Therefore, students must be prepared and always explore the new technology to enhance their learning experience. Based on the British Educational communication and Technology Agency's (Becta's) analysis (2003) electronic copy board machine could have positive effects on teaching. Electronic copy board machine as instructional tool help teacher's many ways. This assistance includes increasing teaching time by allowing teachers to present more than one resource in the lesson and more efficiently (Walker, 2003). ECPM enables teachers to use face-to-face instructions, store and retrieved information at the same time.

Also, students reported that the use of the electronic copy board machine (ECBM) enhances motivation to learn, raises the level of concentration, and enhances learning because it is "fun" and innovative (BECTA, 2008; Cogill, 2002; Hall & Higgins, 2005; Levy, 2002; Morgan, 2008; Thompson & Flecknoe, 2003). Various studies have shown that students who learned with the ECBM were more attentive and engaged in learning, participated more actively in the classroom, and interacted much more with their teachers and their peers (Higgins, Beauchamp, & Miller, 2007; Miller, Glover, & Avris, 2004; Smith, Higgins, Wall, & Miller, 2005). Additional studies provided evidence that the ECBMs serve as significant motivational tools for students and facilitate students' desire to remain on-task (Cooper, 2003; Levy, 2002). Also, Edith & Osnat (2011) and Anulobi, Iwuji & Ihem-Chijoke (2016) opined that electronic copy board machine supports many different learning styles of the students in a variety of learning environments. Electronic copy board machine contributes to cognitive and conceptual developments of the learners and enhances student's positive interest.

Interest is an important variable in learning because when one is interested in an activity, one is likely to perform positively. Chukwu (2001) stated that interest can be expressed through simple statement made by individuals of their like and dislikes. Interest has been defined by Anderson, Shirley, Wilson and Fielding in Unamba (2022) as "the capacity to evoke an emotional response". It is this emotional response that sustains the quests for learning. Olikeze (2021) defined interest as "a persisting tendency to pay attention and enjoy some activities; or content is of interest if it's pleasing and engages one's attention". Anderson et al in Unamba (2022) added that "interest increases attention which, in turn increases learning. Also, Obodo (2002) described interest as the attraction which forces or compels a child to respond to a particular stimulus. This point that a child develops interest if a particular stimulus is attractive and arousing or stimulating This shows that interest comes as a result of eagerness to learn not by force (Harbor Peters, 2002). The development

of interest in basic sciences as an objective of the basic science teaching, may likely promote achievement in the course.

On the issue of gender and academic performance in mathematics there are different views and findings. Researchers like Atouigba, Vershima, O'kwu and Ijenkeli (2012) postulates that there has been global concern about gender differences in students' performance in Mathematics and some researchers have been undertaken in many parts of the globe in this respect. Some researchers have reported gender differences while others have that there is no significant difference in male – female Mathematics performance at any level. Studies conducted in countries of the North have shown that boys performed better than girls and there is significant difference in mathematics (Fennema, 2000 & Kaiser-Messmer, 1994). While Asante 2010 cited studies (Fox, Brody & Tobin, 1980; Hedges & Nowell, 1995; Peterson & Fennema, 1985) showed that boys achieved higher than girls on standardized mathematics tests. However, an interesting body of international literature suggests that female students perform better than male students (Arnot, David & Weiner 1999). Hydea & Mertz (2009) revealed that girls are doing better than boys in mathematical tasks that require problem solving. Unamba, Nwaneri & Nelson (2017) found no significant difference on gender achievement in geometry using 7E as instructional model. Ukaegbu, Unamba & Ugo (2016) found no significant difference on gender achievement in geometry using geogebra software in teaching. Unamba, Onyekwere & Ihekwa (2015) found no significant difference on gender achievement using activity-based learning strategy. Unamba, Onyekwere & Ugochukwu (2017), found no significant difference in achievement motivation and academic achievement engagement of pupils in mathematics classroom. Also, Studies had reported that females exhibited more negative attitude and perceptions towards the use of computers than males (Dambrot, Watkins-Malek, Silling, Marshall & Garver, 1985; Koohang, 1987 in Su-Luan & Atan, 2017). Also, the study by Houtz and Gupta (2001) found significant gender differences between females and males in their ability to master technology skills. Even though both genders were positive about their technological ability, males rated themselves higher than females. In another study, Shashaani and Khalili (2001) reported that female undergraduate students had significantly lower confidence than males when it came to their ability to use computers. Females also reported feeling helpless, nervous and uncomfortable around computers. Tsai, Lin and Tsai (2001) showed no significant gender differences in the perceived usefulness of the Internet. Liaw's study (2002) had also indicated that males had more positive perceptions towards computers and Web technologies than females.

Researchers like Nezih & Cennet (2017) investigated the Use of the Interactive Whiteboard in Mathematics and Mathematics Lessons from the Perspective of Turkish Middle School Students. Results showed that it was concluded that participants' attitudes towards mathematics and the use of the interactive whiteboard was above average. Torff and Tirota (2010) conducted study to determine the extent to which use of interactive whiteboard technology (IWB) was associated with upper elementary students' self-reported level of motivation in mathematics. The study's participants included 773 students (241 students in 4th grade, 260 in 5th grade, and 232 in 6th grade). There were 32 participating teachers: 19 who indicated they were IWB users (the treatment group) and 13 who indicated that they were not extensive users of the IWB (the control group). The treatment group included 458 students and the control group had 315 students. The results of the study revealed that the students in the treatment group reported higher levels of interest relative to control students. Students with teachers who were more supportive of IWB technology reported higher interest levels (compared to students of teachers who were less supportive).

Wall, Higgins, & Smith (2005) conducted survey research in which 80 students filled out templates with questions that asked them what they thought of the IWB and what they were likely to share with others about this technology. A total of 1568 responses were analyzed; 883 of the statements were judged to be positive, 494 statements were scored as neutral, and 191 were judged to be negative. Positive statements were then broken down into subcategories, with “motivation” and “fun” each noted in over 120 responses. The researchers concluded that students deemed the IWB to be motivational and fun, especially when students were able to see their work projected on the IWB screen. Therefore, the main purpose of the study was to investigate utilizing electronic copy machine board as instructional approach on pre-service teacher’s achievement and interest in Mathematics. Specifically, the study determined, whether:

- i. Early childhood care Education Pre-service teachers taught Mathematics using electronic copy machine Board will differ in their achievement from those taught conventionally.
- ii. Male and female early childhood care education pre-service teachers taught mathematics using electronic copy machine board will differ in their achievements.
- iii. Early childhood care education pre-service teacher’s level of interest towards utilizing electronic copy board in learning mathematics.

Research Questions

The following research questions were drawn for the study.

1. What is the difference in mean achievement scores of early childhood care education pre-service teachers taught mathematics utilizing electronic copy board machine and those taught using conventional method?
2. What is the difference in mean achievement scores of male and female early childhood care educations pre-service teachers taught mathematics utilizing electronic copy board machine?
3. What is the interest level of early childhood care education pre-service teacher’s towards utilizing electronic copy board machine in learning of mathematics

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study

1. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of pre-service teachers taught mathematics utilizing electronic copy board machine and those taught conventionally.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female early childhood care educations taught mathematics utilizing electronic copy machine board.

Method

Quasi-experimental research design was adopted for the study. Specifically, the study used non-randomized pretest-posttest group design. Quasi-experimental design was used because intact classes were used instead of randomly composed samples (Oladejo, Olosunde, Ojebisi, & Isola, 2011; Osokoya, 2007; Owusu, Money, Appiah, & Wilmot, 2010). The population of the study comprised of 1,763 pre-service teachers in School of Early Childhood Care Education School, Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education in Owerri Municipal Council of Imo State. A total of 212 pre-service teachers formed the sample for the study. Simple

random sampling technique was used to select two classes of final year NCE (year 3). The experiment groups had 94 students (61 females and 33 males) while the control groups had 118 students (62 females and 56 males). The instruments for data collection were a researcher made 50-item objective test questions titled “Mathematics Achievement Test” (MAT). It was drawn from the topic 2- dimensional and 3- dimensional shapes which were taught the students. The construction of the test instrument was guided by a table of specification. The mathematics interest scale Questionnaire (MISQ) measure student’s interest towards utilizing electronic copy board in learning mathematics, the MISQ consists of 10 items with a 5-point Likert- scale. The MAT and MISQ was subjected to face and content validation. The Mathematics Achievement Test was face validated by specialists in Mathematics Education and Measurement and Evaluation. During the face validation the test was scrutinized in terms of relevance, general test format, suitability and clarity. For the content validation a test blueprint was developed which guided the generation of the test items. Kuder-Richardson 21 reliability coefficient was used to establish the reliability of MAT. The reliability of the test was found to be 0.76 while Cronbach reliability was used to measure MISQ which yield 0.89. The researchers developed two instructional packages for this study. The first instructional package is based on utilizing electronic copy board machine Learning Approach while the second package is based on the conventional method. The two packages were drawn from the same curriculum content. The interactive whiteboard Learning Approach was used for treatment group while the conventional package was used for the control group. At the onset of the experiment, the subjects in both the treatment and control groups were given the pre-test to ensure equity in their cognitive backgrounds. After the pre-test the regular mathematics teachers began the experiment in their respective schools adhering strictly to the lesson procedure that was developed from the instructional package during the pre-experimental training. The teacher guided them through step-by-step tutorial on the features of 2- dimensional and 3- dimensional shapes. Also, solution to problems on area of plane and solid shapes, perimeter and surfaces. The students were allowed to ask questions, make inputs and were cleared at points of need. They were also allowed to identify features of the topic as projected on the board. The technology machine had the ability to reverse the solutions related to problems on distance and bearing relaying the steps for the students to follow. They were also allowed to present problems which were solved by the software and compared with their book solutions. The control groups were taught the same topic by their regular mathematics teacher through the conventional “chalk and talk” approach which was only teacher centered. The process lasted for two weeks after which a post-test was administered on both groups using a rearranged version of the pre-test instrument. The generated data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions while the hypotheses were tested using ANCOVA statistical tool and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question1: What is the difference in mean achievement scores of early childhood care education pre-service teachers taught mathematics utilizing electronic copy board machine and those taught using conventional method?

Table 1: Summary of pre-service teachers mean achievements.

Group	Test	N	Mean	SD	Difference in mean	Diff. in Mean Gain
Expt.	Pretest	94	33.26	8.03	22.79	21.39
	Post test		56.05	18.24		
Control	Pretest	118	31.44	8.16	1.40	
	Post test		32.84	8.03		

Table I shows that the experimental group had a mean achievement gain of 22.79 while the control group had 1.40 this gave a difference of 20.29 difference in favour of the experiment groups.

Research Question 2: What is the difference in mean achievement scores of male and female early childhood care educations pre-service teachers taught mathematics utilizing electronic copy board machine?

Table 2: Summary of mean achievements by gender

Gender	Test	N	Mean	SD	Difference in mean	Diff. in Mean Gain
Male	Pretest	33	32.13	8.04	25.36	2.96
	Post test		57.49	17.94		
Female	Pretest	61	32.88	8.01	22.40	
	Post test		55.28	18.20		

Table 2 shows that, the mean achievement gain of males in the group is 25.36 while the female is 22.40 this gave a slight mean difference of 2.96 in favour of the males in the experimental group.

Research Question 3: What is the interest level of early childhood care education pre-service teacher’s towards utilizing electronic copy board machine in learning of mathematics.

Table 3: Mean scores on interest level

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	I enjoy learning mathematics using electronic copy board machine	3.30	1.05	High level
2	I enjoy practical work using electronic copy board machine	3.54	1.03	High level
3	Learning mathematics concepts using electronic copy board is very interesting	3.00	1.01	High level
4	I really like learning about mathematics.	3.08	0.99	High level
5	Use of electronic copy board machine makes me to discussion about mathematics.	3.06	1.06	High level
6	I feel happy copying notes on any topic related to mathematics because of learning with electronic copy machine.	3.03	1.24	High level
6	Learning using electronic copy machine makes me to attempt any questions based on any topic in mathematics.	3.45	1.06	High level
7	I like telling my friends and peers what I learnt about mathematics.	3.00	1.01	High level
8	The study of mathematics helps to solve problems.	3.00	1,01	High level
9	I am always happy whenever I am copying mathematics lesson using electronic copy machine	3.13	0.86	High level
10	Use of electronic copy machines in learning mathematics control the classroom	3.06	1.06	High level

The result in table 3 shows that all items scored above 2.50. This implies that the interest level of early childhood care education pre-service teacher's towards utilizing electronic copy board machine in learning of mathematics is at high level.

Hypotheses testing

H01: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of pre service teachers taught mathematics utilizing electronic copy board machine and those taught conventionally.

H02: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female early childhood care education taught mathematics utilizing electronic copy machine board.

Table 4: Summary of ANCOVA analysis on Achievement on hypotheses 1 and 2

Source	Type III sum of Squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected model	32296.153	6	32296.153	83.265	.000	
Intercept	27989.317	1	27989.317	432.967	.000	
Covariate	10.660	1	10.660	.165	.685	
Method	27089.804	1	27089.804	419.052	.000	S
Gender	172.535	1	172.535	2.669	.104	NS
Error	13252.314	205	64.645			
Total	425843.000	212				
Corrected Total	45543.467	211				

H01: Table 4 shows that, the calculated f-value for method is 419.05 which is greater than the table value (3.847) also p-value of 0.000 is less than α -value 0.05. Based on the result, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative accepted. This implies that, there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of pre-service teachers taught mathematics using electronic copy board machine and conventional approaches.

H02: Table 4 shows that, the calculated f-value for gender is 2.325 which is less than the table value (3.847), also p-value of 0.10 is greater than α -value of 0.05. Based on the results, the null hypothesis is upheld which implies that no significant difference exists between the mean achievement scores of male and female pre-service teachers taught mathematics utilizing electronic copy board machine.

Discussion

The finding of the study revealed that, students in the experimental group taught mathematics utilizing interactive whiteboard had a better mean achievement scores than their counterparts taught utilizing conventionally through “chalk and talk”. This implies that interactive whiteboard has a better penetrating power in terms of students understanding and interests towards mathematics than the conventional approach. The material also has the ability to liberalize the study of mathematics as it gave room for every student’s participation. The finding is in agreement with Torff and Tirota (2010) showed that interactive white board improves student’s academic achievement. The study also showed that mathematics achievement of male and female students exposed to IWB instructional approach was similar and showed no statistical difference. This is suspected to be as a result of equal learning opportunity which the strategy brought into play. This is in accord with the findings of Ukaegbu, Unamba & Ugo (2016) who found no significant difference on gender achievement in geometry using geogebra software in teaching mathematics. Also, Unamba, Onyekwere & Ihekwa (2015) found no significant difference on gender achievement using activity-based learning strategy. Furthermore, Unamba, Onyekwere & Ugochukwu (2017) found no significant difference in achievement motivation and academic achievement engagement of

pupils in mathematics classroom. The findings indicated that there is no significant difference between male and female science students in each of the attitudinal components towards utilizing interactive white board in mathematics classroom. These results are in line with the findings of Tsai, Lin and Tsai (2001) that there are no significant gender differences in the perceived usefulness of the Internet while Arigbabu & Mji 2004 & Bilesanmi-Awoderu (2006) showed that there are no longer distinguishing differences in the cognitive, affective and psychomotor attitude of students in respect to gender.

Conclusion/ Recommendation

Electronic copy board helps students to have opportunity to grasp the essential information during instructional delivery. It encourages students to embrace technology in their learning. This not only benefits the student in the short-term providing access to a wider base of knowledge, but it also helps them to stay on the cutting edge of technology as the year's progress so they may learn the essential skills to take a viable role in the future workplace. Using electronic educational environment and copy board, teacher could use technological educational materials such as film, picture, slide and educational software in planning lessons; teaching-learning process and evaluation to enhance quality and durability of education. The study concludes that electronic copy board enhanced pre-service teacher's achievement and interest in mathematics across gender. It was recommended that; Teachers should understand their students in the classroom so that they will know the approaches to be applied when teaching mathematics. The State Ministry of Education should organize seminars and workshops to educate mathematics teachers about the benefits of utilizing ICTs in teaching, especially electronic copy board machine.

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